

Kernel and Weakly Ultra-Separated Relationship with Separation Axioms in Stable Neutrosophic Crisp Topological Spaces

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Abstract: This paper highlights the separation of axioms in neutrosophic crisp where it is defined as the regular and normal in this space with respect to four different neutrosophic points $(\mathbb{P}^{\mathcal{N}_1}, \dots, \mathbb{P}^{\mathcal{N}_4})$. We supported these concepts with their most important topological properties. The important part of the work is defining two concepts kernel and weakly ultra-separated and their relationship with T_0, T_1 and T_2 spaces under the idea of four different neutrosophic points. The results were exceptional, and this work was supported by various examples.

Keywords: regular, normal, kernel and weakly ultra-separated and their relationship with T_0, T_1 and T_2 spaces in neutrosophic crisp sets.

1. Introduction

Salama and Florentin [1] defined three distinct kinds of neutrosophic crisp set. The first type requires the condition

$$\mathbb{K}_1 \cap \mathbb{K}_2 = \emptyset, \mathbb{K}_1 \cap \mathbb{K}_3 = \emptyset, \mathbb{K}_2 \cap \mathbb{K}_3 = \emptyset$$

to which we give the symbol $(NCSs^1)$. While the second type symbolized $(NCSs^2)$, which requires the condition

$$\mathbb{K}_1 \cap \mathbb{K}_2 = \emptyset, \mathbb{K}_1 \cap \mathbb{K}_3 = \emptyset, \mathbb{K}_2 \cap \mathbb{K}_3 = \emptyset, \text{ and } \mathbb{K}_1 \cup \mathbb{K}_2 \cup \mathbb{K}_3 = X$$

and the third type $(NCSs^3)$ requires the condition

$$\mathbb{K}_1 \cap \mathbb{K}_2 \cap \mathbb{K}_3 = \emptyset \text{ and } \mathbb{K}_1 \cup \mathbb{K}_2 \cup \mathbb{K}_3 = X.$$

Moreover, through their research they defined types of empty sets, which are:

$$\emptyset_1^{\mathcal{N}} = \langle\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, X \rangle\rangle, \emptyset_2^{\mathcal{N}} = \langle\langle \emptyset, X, \emptyset \rangle\rangle, \emptyset_3^{\mathcal{N}} = \langle\langle \emptyset, X, X \rangle\rangle, \emptyset_4^{\mathcal{N}} = \langle\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\rangle$$

and synonymously they defined types of comprehensive sets and their forms are given

$$X_1^{\mathcal{N}} = \langle\langle X, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\rangle, X_2^{\mathcal{N}} = \langle\langle X, X, \emptyset \rangle\rangle, X_3^{\mathcal{N}} = \langle\langle X, \emptyset, X \rangle\rangle, X_4^{\mathcal{N}} = \langle\langle X, X, X \rangle\rangle$$

As for the complement of any neutrosophic crisp set, there are three types:

$$(\mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}})^{C_1} = \langle\langle \mathbb{K}_1^C, \mathbb{K}_2^C, \mathbb{K}_3^C \rangle\rangle, (\mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}})^{C_2} = \langle\langle \mathbb{K}_3, \mathbb{K}_2, \mathbb{K}_1 \rangle\rangle, \text{ and } (\mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}})^{C_3} = \langle\langle \mathbb{K}_3, \mathbb{K}_2^C, \mathbb{K}_1 \rangle\rangle.$$

Salama and Florentin [1] defined the first and second subsets as follows:

$$(\mathbb{L}^{\mathcal{N}} \subseteq_1 \mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}}) \text{ if and only if } \mathbb{L}_1 \subseteq \mathbb{K}_1, \mathbb{L}_2 \subseteq \mathbb{K}_2, \mathbb{L}_3 \supseteq \mathbb{K}_3$$

and

$$(\mathbb{L}^{\mathcal{N}} \subseteq_2 \mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}}) \text{ if and only if } \mathbb{L}_1 \subseteq \mathbb{K}_1, \mathbb{L}_2 \supseteq \mathbb{K}_2, \mathbb{L}_3 \supseteq \mathbb{K}_3.$$

While the union and intersection were defined as follows:

$$\mathbb{L}^{\mathcal{N}} \cup_1 \mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}} = \langle\langle \mathbb{L}_1 \cup \mathbb{K}_1, \mathbb{L}_2 \cup \mathbb{K}_2, \mathbb{L}_3 \cap \mathbb{K}_3 \rangle\rangle$$

$$\mathbb{L}^{\mathcal{N}} \cup_2 \mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}} = \langle\langle \mathbb{L}_1 \cup \mathbb{K}_1, \mathbb{L}_2 \cap \mathbb{K}_2, \mathbb{L}_3 \cap \mathbb{K}_3 \rangle\rangle$$

$$\mathbb{L}^{\mathcal{N}} \cap_1 \mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}} = \langle\langle \mathbb{L}_1 \cap \mathbb{K}_1, \mathbb{L}_2 \cap \mathbb{K}_2, \mathbb{L}_3 \cup \mathbb{K}_3 \rangle\rangle$$

$$\mathbb{L}^{\mathcal{N}} \cap_2 \mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}} = \langle\langle \mathbb{L}_1 \cap \mathbb{K}_1, \mathbb{L}_2 \cup \mathbb{K}_2, \mathbb{L}_3 \cup \mathbb{K}_3 \rangle\rangle$$

and they defined two types of points that are:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}^{\mathcal{N}_1} &= \ll \{\mathbb{P}\}, \emptyset, \{\mathbb{P}\}^c \gg \\ \mathbb{P}^{\mathcal{N}_2} &= \ll \emptyset, \{\mathbb{P}\}, \{\mathbb{P}\}^c \gg. \end{aligned}$$

However, they do not cover a complete area in relation to space, therefore, we decided to add two additional definitions of types of points, namely

$$\mathbb{P}^{\mathcal{N}_3} = \ll \{\mathbb{P}\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \gg \text{ and } \mathbb{P}^{\mathcal{N}_4} = \ll \emptyset, \{\mathbb{P}\}, \emptyset \gg$$

where $\{\mathbb{P}\}$ is singleton [2].

As for the belonging of points to sets, they were used as follows:

- i. $\mathbb{P}^{\mathcal{N}_1} \in_1 \mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}}$ if and only if $\mathbb{P} \in \mathbb{K}_1$ and $\mathbb{P} \notin \mathbb{K}_3$
- ii. $\mathbb{P}^{\mathcal{N}_2} \in_2 \mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}}$ if and only if $\mathbb{P} \in \mathbb{K}_2$ and $\mathbb{P} \notin \mathbb{K}_3$
- iii. $\mathbb{P}^{\mathcal{N}_3} \in_3 \mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}}$ if and only if $\mathbb{P} \in \mathbb{K}_1$
- iv. $\mathbb{P}^{\mathcal{N}_4} \in_4 \mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}}$ if and only if $\mathbb{P} \in \mathbb{K}_2$ and not belonging to NCSs
- v. $\mathbb{P}^{\mathcal{N}_1} \notin_1 \mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}}$ if and only if $\mathbb{P} \notin \mathbb{K}_1$ and $\mathbb{P} \in \mathbb{K}_3$
- vi. $\mathbb{P}^{\mathcal{N}_2} \notin_2 \mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}}$ if and only if $\mathbb{P} \notin \mathbb{K}_2$ and $\mathbb{P} \in \mathbb{K}_3$
- vii. $\mathbb{P}^{\mathcal{N}_3} \notin_3 \mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}}$ if and only if $\mathbb{P} \notin \mathbb{K}_1$
- viii. $\mathbb{P}^{\mathcal{N}_4} \notin_4 \mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}}$ if and only if $\mathbb{P} \notin \mathbb{K}_2$

There are many researchers and academics who have worked in the field of neutrosophic crisp set theory [3-6]. However, these works don't light out on what we did in this paper. The above conditions are employed to define new concepts and properties in our work such as the concepts and properties of regular, normal, kernel and weakly ultra-separated.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1:[7]

Let X be a fixed set that is not empty, then a \mathcal{SNCT} -space is a family $T_x^{\mathcal{N}}$ satisfies the following condition:

- i. $\emptyset_3^{\mathcal{N}}, X_1^{\mathcal{N}} \in T_x^{\mathcal{N}}$
- ii. $\forall \mathbb{L}^{\mathcal{N}}, \mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}} \in T_x^{\mathcal{N}}, \exists \mathbb{H}^{\mathcal{N}} \in T_x^{\mathcal{N}}, \exists \mathbb{H}^{\mathcal{N}} \subseteq_1 \mathbb{L}^{\mathcal{N}} \cap_2 \mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}}$
- iii. $\forall \mathbb{L}_i^{\mathcal{N}} \in T_x^{\mathcal{N}}, \exists \mathbb{F}^{\mathcal{N}} \in T_x^{\mathcal{N}} \ni \mathbb{F}^{\mathcal{N}} \subseteq_1 \cup_2 \mathbb{L}_i^{\mathcal{N}}, i = 1, \dots, n$

then $(X, T_x^{\mathcal{N}})$ is a (\mathcal{SNCT} -space). For any $\mathbb{K}^{\mathcal{N}} \in T_x^{\mathcal{N}}$ to be a stable neutrosophic crisp open set and it's denoted by (\mathcal{SNCO} -set), the complement of type 1,3 for (\mathcal{SNCO} -set) is stable neutrosophic crisp closed set and denoted by (\mathcal{SNCC} -set).

Definition 2.2:[7]

Let $(X, T_x^{\mathcal{N}})$ be a \mathcal{SNCT} -space and $A^{\mathcal{N}}$ be aNCSs, then the stable interior of $A^{\mathcal{N}}$ denoted by $\mathcal{S}i_{ij}(A^{\mathcal{N}})$, define as:

$$\mathcal{S}i_{ij}(A^{\mathcal{N}}) = \cup_i \{ \mathcal{R}^{\mathcal{N}} \in T_x^{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{R}^{\mathcal{N}} \subseteq_j A^{\mathcal{N}} \}, i, j = 1, 2$$

Definition 2.3:

Let $(X, T_x^{\mathcal{N}})$ be a \mathcal{SNCT} -space and $A^{\mathcal{N}}$ be a NCSs, then the stable exterior of $A^{\mathcal{N}}$ denoted by $\mathcal{S}e_{ij}(A^{\mathcal{N}})$, define as:

$$\mathcal{S}e_{ij}(A^{\mathcal{N}}) = \mathcal{S}i_{ij}((A^{\mathcal{N}})^{c_l}) \quad i, j = 1, 2; l = 1, 3$$

Definition 2.4:

Let $(X, T_x^{\mathcal{N}})$ be a \mathcal{SNCT} -space and $A^{\mathcal{N}}$ be a NCSs, then the stable closure of $A^{\mathcal{N}}$ denoted by $\mathcal{S}\mathcal{C}l_{ij}(A^{\mathcal{N}})$, define as:

$$\mathcal{S}\mathcal{C}l_{ij}(A^{\mathcal{N}}) = \left(\mathcal{S}e_{ij}(A^{\mathcal{N}}) \right)^{c_l} \quad i, j = 1, 2; l = 1, 3$$

Definition 2.5:

Any $A^{\mathcal{N}}$ is said to be \mathcal{SNC} compact if and only if every \mathcal{SNC} open cover of $A^{\mathcal{N}}$ has a finite subcover. That is, for every collection $\{G_\lambda^{\mathcal{N}} : \lambda \in \Lambda\}$ of \mathcal{SNCO} such that $A^{\mathcal{N}} \subseteq_1 \cup_2 \{G_\lambda^{\mathcal{N}} : \lambda \in \Lambda\}$, then there exist finitely many sets $G_{\lambda_1}^{\mathcal{N}}, \dots, G_{\lambda_n}^{\mathcal{N}}$ of \mathcal{SNCO} such that $A^{\mathcal{N}} \subseteq_1 G_{\lambda_1}^{\mathcal{N}} \cup_2 \dots \cup_2 G_{\lambda_n}^{\mathcal{N}}$. In particular, \mathcal{SNCT} is said to be \mathcal{SNC} compact if and only if for every collection $\{G_\lambda^{\mathcal{N}} : \lambda \in \Lambda\}$ of \mathcal{SNCO} sets for which $X_1^{\mathcal{N}} = \cup_2 \{G_\lambda^{\mathcal{N}} : \lambda \in \Lambda\}$, then there exist finitely many sets $G_{\lambda_1}^{\mathcal{N}}, \dots, G_{\lambda_n}^{\mathcal{N}}$ of \mathcal{SNCO} such

that $X_1^N = G_{\lambda_1}^N \cup_2 \dots \cup_2 G_{\lambda_n}^N$. It is case to see that a finite union of SNC compact sets is SNC compact.

Definition 2.6:

Let $\mathcal{F}: (X, T_x^N) \rightarrow (Y, T_y^N)$ be a function and for any $B^N = \langle\langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle\rangle$ to be a SNCSSs in Y , then the preimage of B^N under \mathcal{F} denoted by $\mathcal{F}^{-1}(B^N)$ is a SNCSSs in X defined by $\mathcal{F}^{-1}(B^N) = \langle\langle \mathcal{F}^{-1}(B_1), \mathcal{F}^{-1}(B_2), \mathcal{F}^{-1}(B_3) \rangle\rangle$. If $A^N = \langle\langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle\rangle$ is a SNCSSs in X , then the image of A^N under \mathcal{F} denoted by $\mathcal{F}(A^N)$ is the a SNCSSs in Y defined by $\mathcal{F}(A^N) = \langle\langle \mathcal{F}(A_1), \mathcal{F}(A_2), \mathcal{F}(A_3) \rangle\rangle$.

Definition 2.7:

Let (X, T_x^N) and (Y, T_y^N) be two SNCTS and let $\mathcal{F}: X \rightarrow Y$ be a function \mathcal{F} , then \mathcal{F} is said to be SNC continuous if the preimage of each SNCSSs in T_y^N is a SNCSSs in T_x^N .

Definition 2.8:

Let (X, T_x^N) and (Y, T_y^N) be two SNCTS and let \mathcal{F} be a mapping of X into Y . Then \mathcal{F} is said to be SNCO mapping if and only if $\mathcal{F}(G^N)$ is T_y^N SNCO_{set} whenever G^N is T_x^N SNCO_{set}.

Definition 2.9:

Let (X, T_x^N) and (Y, T_y^N) be two SNCTS and let \mathcal{F} be a mapping of X into Y . Then \mathcal{F} is said to be SNCC mapping if and only if $\mathcal{F}(G^N)$ is T_y^N SNCC_{set} whenever G^N is T_x^N SNCC_{set}.

Definition 2.10:

Let (X, T_x^N) and (Y, T_y^N) be two SNCTS and let \mathcal{F} be a mapping of X into Y . Then \mathcal{F} is said to be SNC – bicontinuous if and only if \mathcal{F} is SNCO and SNCC – continuous.

Definition 2.11:

Let (X, T_x^N) and (Y, T_y^N) be two SNCTS and let \mathcal{F} be a mapping of X into Y . Then \mathcal{F} is said to be SNC – homeomorphism if and only if

- i. \mathcal{F} is bijective, that is, one-one and onto,
- ii. \mathcal{F} is $T_x^N - T_y^N$ SNC – continuous,
- iii. \mathcal{F}^{-1} is $T_y^N - T_x^N$ SNC – continuous.

Definition 2.12:

A space X is said to be SNC – homeomorphic to another space Y if there exists SNC – homeomorphism of X onto Y . Moreover, Y is said to be SNC – homeomorphic image of X or simply a SNC – homeomorphic of X if (X, T_x^N) is SNC – homeomorphic to (Y, T_y^N) and we write it as $(X, T_x^N) \approx (Y, T_y^N)$.

Definition 2.13:

A SNCTS (X, T_x^N) is said to be SNC – T_0 space with respect to SNC – points (for kinds) if and only if

$$\forall \mathbb{P}^{N_i} \neq \mathbb{Q}^{N_i}, \mathbb{P}^{N_i}, \mathbb{Q}^{N_i} \in \text{NCP}_s \exists G^N \in T_x^N \ni \mathbb{P}^{N_i} \in_i G^N, \mathbb{Q}^{N_i} \notin_i G^N, i = 1,2,3,4$$

Definition 2.14:

A SNCTS (X, T_x^N) is said to be SNC – T_1 space with respect to SNC – points (for kinds) if and only if

$$\forall \mathbb{P}^{N_i} \neq \mathbb{Q}^{N_i}, \mathbb{P}^{N_i}, \mathbb{Q}^{N_i} \in \text{NCP}_s \exists G^N, H^N \in T_x^N \ni \mathbb{P}^{N_i} \in_i G^N, \mathbb{Q}^{N_i} \notin_i G^N \text{ and } \mathbb{P}^{N_i} \notin_i H^N, \mathbb{Q}^{N_i} \in_i H^N, i = 1,2,3,4.$$

Definition 2.15:

A SNCTS (X, T_x^N) is said to be SNC – T_2 space with respect to SNC – points (for kinds) if and only if

$$\forall \mathbb{P}^{N_i} \neq \mathbb{Q}^{N_i}, \mathbb{P}^{N_i}, \mathbb{Q}^{N_i} \in \text{NCP}_s \exists G^N, H^N \in T_x^N \ni \mathbb{P}^{N_i} \in_i G^N, \mathbb{Q}^{N_i} \in_i H^N, i = 1,2,3,4 \text{ and } G^N \cap_2 H^N = \emptyset_3^N.$$

3. Separation Axioms

In this section, we will address the definition and study of the properties of regular and normal in the general and special case with the four points. Moreover, we study kernel and weakly ultra-separated set in the neutrosophic crisp set theory and the relationship with the separation axioms.

Definition 3.1:

A stable neutrosophic crisp topological space (X, T_x^N) is said to be SNC – regular space if and only if for every SNCC set F^N and $\forall NCP_s \mathbb{p}^{Ni} \notin F^N$,

$$\exists G^N, H^N \in T_x^N, \text{ such that } F^N \subseteq_1 G^N, \mathbb{p}^{Ni} \in_1 H^N \text{ and } G^N \cap_2 H^N = \emptyset_3^N, i = 1,2,3,4$$

Definition 3.2:

If (X, T_x^N) is SNC – regular space and SNC – T_2 space, then it is called SNC – T_3 space.

Proposition 3.3:

Let (X, T_x^N) be singularly SNCC and SNC – regular space, then it is a SNC – T_2 space.

Proof: Proof is obvious.

Proposition 3.4:

Let $\mathcal{F}: (X, T_x^N) \rightarrow (Y, T_y^N)$ be SNC – homeomorphic if (X, T_x^N) is a SNC – regular space. Then (Y, T_y^N) is a SNC – regular space.

Proof:

Let F^N be a T_y^N – SNCC set and let \mathbb{q}^{Ni} be a NCP_s of Y such that $\mathbb{q}^{Ni} \notin F^N$. Since \mathcal{F} is one-one onto mapping $\exists \mathbb{p}^{Ni} \in_1 X$ such that $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{p}^{Ni}) = \mathbb{q}^{Ni}$ if and only if $\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\mathbb{q}^{Ni}) = \mathbb{p}^{Ni}, i = 1,2,3,4$. Again, since \mathcal{F} is SNC – continuous mapping, then $\mathcal{F}^{-1}(F^N)$ is T_x^N – SNCC set and also $\mathbb{q}^{Ni} \notin F^N$, then $\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\mathbb{q}^{Ni}) \notin \mathcal{F}^{-1}(F^N)$, and $\mathbb{p}^{Ni} \notin \mathcal{F}^{-1}(F^N)$. Thus, $\mathcal{F}^{-1}(F^N)$ is a T_x^N – SNCC set and \mathbb{p}^{Ni} is NCP_s of X such that $\mathbb{p}^{Ni} \notin \mathcal{F}^{-1}(F^N)$.

Since (X, T_x^N) is a SNC – regular space, then there exists $G^N, H^N \in T_x^N$ such that

$$\mathbb{p}^{Ni} \in_1 G^N, \mathcal{F}^{-1}(F^N) \subseteq_1 H^N \text{ and } G^N \cap_2 H^N = \emptyset_3^N$$

Now, $\mathbb{p}^{Ni} \notin G^N$, then $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{p}^{Ni}) = \mathbb{q}^{Ni} \notin \mathcal{F}(G^N)$. Since $\mathcal{F}^{-1}(F^N) \subseteq_1 H^N$, then

$$\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{F}^{-1}(F^N)) \subseteq_1 \mathcal{F}(H^N).$$

This leads us to $F^N \subseteq_1 \mathcal{F}(H^N)$ and $G^N \cap_2 H^N = \emptyset_3^N$ and then $\mathcal{F}(G^N \cap_2 H^N) = \mathcal{F}(\emptyset_3^N)$ and $\mathcal{F}(G^N) \cap_2 \mathcal{F}(H^N) = \emptyset_3^N$.

Also, since \mathcal{F} is a SNC – open map $\mathcal{F}(G^N)$, then we have that $\mathcal{F}(H^N)$ are T_y^N – SNCO sets. Thus (Y, T_y^N) is a SNC – regular space.

Proposition 3.5:

Let (X, T_x^N) be a SNC – regular space and $Y \subseteq_1 X$ then (Y, T_y^N) is a SNC – regular space.

Proof: Proof is obvious.

Example 3.6:

The property of space being a SNC – T_3 space is hereditary.

Solution:

Suppose (X, T_x^N) is a SNC – T_3 space and $Y \subseteq_1 X$. Now, X is a SNC – regular space as well as a SNC – T_1 space. Since, we have shown that both these properties are hereditary, then it follows that SNC – T_3 space is SNC – regular space as well as a SNC – T_1 space and hence it is a SNC – T_3 space.

Proposition 3.7:

Every SNC – compact space and SNC – T_2 space is SNC – T_3 space.

Proof:

Let (X, T_x^N) be a SNC – compact space. Since, a SNC – T_2 space is a SNC – T_1 space. It suffices to show that (X, T_x^N) is SNC – regular space. Let F^N is SNCC subset of X , then $\mathbb{p}^{Ni} \in_1 X, i = 1,2,3,4$, such that $\mathbb{p}^{Ni} \notin F^N$.

So that, $\mathbb{p}^{Ni} \in_1 (F^N)^{C_1}$ and since X is SNC – T_2 space for each $\mathbb{q}^{Ni} \in_1 F^N$. There exist $G^N, H^N \in T_x^N$ such that $\mathbb{p}^{Ni} \in_1 G^N, \mathbb{q}^{Ni} \in_1 H^N$ and $G^N \cap_2 H^N = \emptyset_3^N$. The next collection $C^N = \{H^N: \mathbb{q}^{Ni} \in_1 F^N\}$ is evidently T_x^N – SNCO cover of F^N . Since F^N is a SNCC subset of SNC – compact space X , it follows that F^N is SNC – compact space, hence there exists a finite number of points $\mathbb{q}_1^{Ni}, \mathbb{q}_2^{Ni}, \dots, \mathbb{q}_n^{Ni} \in_1 F^N$, such that

$$F^N \subseteq_1 \cup_{j=1}^n H_{\mathbb{q}_j^{Ni}}^N$$

Let

$$M^N = \cup_{j=1}^n H_{\mathbb{Q}_j^N}^N, Q^N = \cap_{j=1}^n G_{\mathbb{Q}_j^N}^N$$

then $\mathbb{P}^N \in_i Q^N$ and $\mathbb{P}^N \in_i G^N$ for each \mathbb{Q}_j^N . Also, we have Q^N and $M^N \in T_x^N$ such that $Q^N \cap_2 M^N = \emptyset_3^N$, then (X, T_x^N) is $\text{SNC} - \text{regular space}$.

Proposition 3.8:

Let X be $\text{SNC} - \text{regular space}$ and let A^N be a $\text{SNC} - \text{compact subset}$ of X . If G^N is SNCO set containing A^N , then there exists a SNCC set H^N such that $A^N \subseteq_1 H^N \subseteq_1 G^N$.

Proof: Proof is obvious.

Proposition 3.9:

Let X be $\text{SNC} - \text{regular space}$ then for any NCP_s , $\mathbb{P}^N \in_i G^N \in T_x^N$
 $\exists M^N \in T_x^N, \mathbb{P}^N \in_i G^N \subseteq_1 \mathcal{G}_{22}(M^N) \subseteq_1 G^N$

Example 3.10:

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ be a set and let $\hat{A}^N = \ll \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}, \{c\} \gg, \hat{B}^N = \ll \{c\}, \{a\}, \{a, b\} \gg, \hat{C}^N = \ll \{c, a\}, \{a\}, \{b\} \gg, \hat{D}^N = \ll \{a\}, X, \{b, c\} \gg$ be $\text{SNCO} - \text{set}$, then we set the following collection $T_x^N = \{\hat{A}^N, \hat{B}^N, \hat{C}^N, \hat{D}^N, \emptyset_3^N, X_1^N\}$ is a $\text{SNCT} - \text{space}$.

Definition 3.11:

A stable neutrosophic crisp topological space (X, T_x^N) is said to be $\text{SNC} - \text{normal space}$ if and only if for every SNCC sets L^N and M^N such that $L^N \cap_2 M^N = \emptyset_3^N$, then there exists SNCO sets $G^N, H^N \in T_x^N$ such that $L^N \subseteq_1 G^N, M^N \subseteq_1 H^N$ and $G^N \cap_2 H^N = \emptyset_3^N$.

Definition 3.12:

If (X, T_x^N) is $\text{SNC} - \text{normal space}$ and $\text{SNC} - T_1$ space, then it called $\text{SNC} - T_4$ space.

Proposition 3.13:

Let $\mathcal{F}: (X, T_x^N) \rightarrow (Y, T_y^N)$ be $\text{SNC} - \text{homeomorphic}$ if (X, T_x^N) is a $\text{SNC} - \text{normal space}$, then (Y, T_y^N) is a $\text{SNC} - \text{normal space}$.

Proof: Proof is obvious.

Proposition 3.14:

Every SNCC subsets of $\text{SNC} - \text{normal space}$ is $\text{SNC} - \text{normal space}$

Proof:

Let (X, T_x^N) be a $\text{SNC} - \text{normal space}$ and (Y, T_y^N) be a $\text{SNC} - \text{subspace}$. Let $L^N \neq M^N$ be a $T_y^N - \text{SNCC}$ subset of Y then there exists $T_y^N - \text{SNCC}$ subset K^N, H^N of X such that $L^N = H^N \cap_2 Y$ and $M^N = K^N \cap_2 Y$. Since Y is $T_y^N - \text{SNCC}$ set, then it follows that $L^N \neq M^N$ and

$T_y^N - \text{SNCC}$ subset of X then by $\text{SNC} - \text{normality}$ of X . There exists $T_x^N - \text{SNCO}$ subset G^N, F^N of X such that, $L^N \subseteq_1 G^N, M^N \subseteq_1 F^N$ and $G^N \cap_2 F^N = \emptyset_3^N, L^N \subseteq_1 Y, M^N \subseteq_1 Y$. These relations imply that, $L^N \subseteq_1 G^N \cap_2 Y, M^N \subseteq_1 F^N \cap_2 Y$ and $(G^N \cap_2 Y) \cap_2 (F^N \cap_2 Y) = \emptyset_3^N$. Setting $G^N \cap_2 Y = E^N$ and $F^N \cap_2 Y = J^N$, we see that E^N, J^N are $T_y^N - \text{SNCO}$ subset of Y such that $L^N \subseteq_1 E^N, M^N \subseteq_1 J^N$ and $E^N \cap_2 J^N = \emptyset_3^N$. Thus, (Y, T_y^N) is a $\text{SNC} - \text{normal space}$.

Proposition 3.15:

Let (X, T_x^N) is a $\text{SNC} - \text{normal space}$ if and only if for any SNCC set F^N and SNCO set G^N containing F^N , there exists, SNCO set V^N such that $F^N \subseteq_1 V^N$ and $\mathcal{G}_{22}(V^N) \subseteq_1 G^N$ or $F^N \subseteq_1 V^N \subseteq_1 \mathcal{G}_{22}(V^N) \subseteq_1 G^N$.

Proof: Proof is obvious.

Proposition 3.16:

Every $\text{SNC} - T_4$ space is singularly SNCC space is also $\text{SNC} - T_3$ space.

Proof:

Let (X, T_x^N) be a $\text{SNC} - T_4$ space is singularly SNCC space. Then (X, T_x^N) is a $\text{SNC} - \text{normal space}$ as well as $\text{SNC} - T_1$ space. Let F^N be a SNCC subset of X and let \mathbb{P}^N be SNCO of X such that $\mathbb{P}^N \notin_i F^N$. Since (X, T_x^N) is singularly, then $\text{SNCC} \{\mathbb{P}^N\}$ is SNCC subset of X such that $\{\mathbb{P}^N\} \cap_2 F^N = \emptyset_3^N, i = 1, 2, 3, 4$ [by $\text{SNC} - \text{normality}$]. Thus, there exist SNCO sets G^N, H^N such that $\{\mathbb{P}^N\} \subseteq_1 G^N, F^N \subseteq_1 H^N$ and $G^N \cap_2 H^N = \emptyset_3^N$. Moreover, $\{\mathbb{P}^N\} \subseteq_1 G^N$, then $\mathbb{P}^N \in_i G^N$. Thus, there exist SNCO sets G^N, H^N such that $\mathbb{P}^N \in_i G^N, F^N \subseteq_1 H^N$ and $G^N \cap_2 H^N = \emptyset_3^N$, then (X, T_x^N) is a $\text{SNC} - \text{regular space}$.

Proposition 3.17:

Every SNC – compact space and SNC – T₂ space is SNC – normal space.

Proof: Proof is obvious.

Example 3.18:

Reconsider Example 3.10.

Definition 3.19:

The intersection of all SNCO subset of SNC space (X, T_x^N) containing A^N is called the SNC – kernel of A^N, This means that

$$\mathcal{Ker}(A^N) = \cap_2 \{G^N \in T_x^N : A^N \subseteq_1 G^N\}$$

Example 3.20:

Reconsider Example 3.10 and let H^N = << {a}, {b, c}, {a, c} >> and K^N = << {c}, {a}, X >> then $\mathcal{Ker}(H^N) = \hat{A}^N$ and $\mathcal{Ker}(K^N) = \hat{B}^N \cap_2 \hat{C}^N = \ll \{c\}, \{a\}, \{a, b\} \gg = \hat{B}^N$.

Definition 3.21:

In SNC space (X, T_x^N), a set A^N is said to be SNC – weakly ultra separated from B^N if there exists a SNCO set G^N such that A^N ⊆₁ G^N and G^N ∩₂ B^N = ∅₃^N or A^N ∩₂ ∩₂₂(B^N) = ∅₃^N.

Example 3.22:

Reconsider example 3.20 and let

$$K^N = \ll \{c\}, \{a\}, X \gg \subseteq_1 \hat{B}^N = \ll \{c\}, \{a\}, \{a, b\} \gg, \hat{B}^N \cap_2 H^N = \ll \emptyset, X, X \gg = \emptyset_3^N$$

then K^N is SNC – weakly ultra separated from H^N.

Definition 3.23:

∀ G^N ∈ T_x^N, A^N ⊆₁ G^N, G^N ∩₂ B^N ≠ ∅₃^N or A^N ∩₂ ∩₂₂(B^N) ≠ ∅₃^N if and only if A^N is not SNC – weakly ultra separated from B^N

Example 3.24:

Reconsider Example 3.10

Remark 3.25:

For every two distinct point p^{N_i} and q^{N_j} of X, i, j = 1, 2, 3

$$\mathcal{Ker}\{p^{N_i}\} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} q^{N_j} : \{p^{N_i}\} \text{ is not} \\ \text{SNC – weakly ultra separated from } \{q^{N_j}\} \end{array} \right\}$$

Remark 3.26:

- i. q^{N₄} of X, $\mathcal{Ker}\{p^{N_4}\} = \{q^{N_4} : \{p^{N_4}\}\}$ with condition each $G^N \in T(q^{N_4})$ G₂ ≠ X or G₃ ≠ X and H^N ∈ T(q^N) H₂ ≠ X or H₃ ≠ X
- ii. If A^N ⊆₁ B^N then $\mathcal{Ker}\{A^N\} \subseteq_1 \mathcal{Ker}\{B^N\}$
- iii. $\mathcal{Ker}(A^N) = \{p^{N_i} \in_i X; A^N \cap_2 \cap_{22}(p^{N_i}) \neq \emptyset_3^N\}$
- iv. Let q^{N_j} ∈_j $\mathcal{Ker}\{p^{N_i}\}$ if and only if p^{N_i} ∈_i ∩₂₂(q^{N_j})

Proof:

We will proof point (iv) and leave the rest without proof because it is clear. Let q^{N_j} ∈_j $\mathcal{Ker}\{p^{N_i}\}$ if and only if ∀ G^N ∈ T_x^N then q^{N_j} ∈_j G^N if and only if ∀ G^N ∈ T_x^N then p^{N_i} ∈_i G^N if and only if p^{N_i} ∈_i ∩₂₂(q^{N_j}).

Remark 3.27:

The following statements are equivalent for any two NCP p^{N_i} and q^{N_j} in a SNC – space (X, T_x^N) :

$$1) \mathcal{Ker}\{p^{N_i}\} \neq \mathcal{Ker}\{q^{N_j}\} \quad 2) \cap_{22}\{p^{N_i}\} \neq \cap_{22}\{q^{N_j}\}$$

Remark 3.28:

$$\mathcal{Ker}(\mathcal{Ker}(A^N)) = \mathcal{Ker}(A^N) \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4$$

Proof:

By defined kernel and Remark 3.26 (2), since A^N ⊆₁ $\mathcal{Ker}(A^N)$, then

$$\mathcal{Ker}(A^N) \subseteq_1 \mathcal{Ker}(\mathcal{Ker}(A^N)) \text{ and } A^N \subseteq_1 V^N, j = 1, 2, 3, 4$$

then

$$\mathcal{Ker}(A^N) \subseteq_1 \mathcal{Ker}(V^N) = V^N.$$

Hence q^{N_j} ∉_j $\mathcal{Ker}(\mathcal{Ker}(A^N))$. Then $\mathcal{Ker}(\mathcal{Ker}(A^N)) \subseteq_1 \mathcal{Ker}(A^N)$

Proposition 3.29:

Let (X, T_x^N) be a SNC – T_0 space if and only if either $\mathcal{Ker}\{\mathbb{P}^{N_i}\}$ is SNC – weakly ultra separated from $\{\mathcal{Q}^{N_i}\}$ or $\mathcal{Ker}\{\mathcal{Q}^{N_i}\}$ is SNC – weakly ultra separated from $\{\mathbb{P}^{N_i}\}$ for each $\mathbb{P}^{N_i} \neq \mathcal{Q}^{N_i} \in_i G^N$.

Proof:

Let (X, T_x^N) be a SNC – T_0 space then for each $\mathbb{P}^{N_i} \neq \mathcal{Q}^{N_i} \in_i G^N$, then there exists SNCO set $G^N \ni \mathbb{P}^{N_i} \in_i G^N, \mathcal{Q}^{N_i} \notin_i G^N$ or $\mathbb{P}^{N_i} \notin_i G^N, \mathcal{Q}^{N_i} \in_i G^N, i = 1, 2, 3, 4$. Now, if $\mathbb{P}^{N_i} \in_i G^N, \mathcal{Q}^{N_i} \notin_i G^N$ implies $\mathcal{Ker}\{\mathbb{P}^{N_i}\}$ is SNC – weakly ultra separated from $\{\mathcal{Q}^{N_i}\}$ or $\mathbb{P}^{N_i} \notin_i G^N, \mathcal{Q}^{N_i} \in_i G^N$ implies $\mathcal{Ker}\{\mathcal{Q}^{N_i}\}$ SNC – weakly ultra separated from $\{\mathbb{P}^{N_i}\}$.

Conversely, let $\mathcal{Ker}\{\mathbb{P}^{N_i}\}$ be a SNC – weakly ultra separated from $\{\mathcal{Q}^{N_i}\}$ or $\mathcal{Ker}\{\mathcal{Q}^{N_i}\}$ SNC – weakly ultra separated from $\{\mathbb{P}^{N_i}\}$, then \exists SNCO set $G^N \ni \mathcal{Ker}\{\mathbb{P}^{N_i}\} \subseteq_1 G^N$ and $G^N \cap_2 \{\mathcal{Q}^{N_i}\} = \emptyset_3^N$ [by definition 3.21] implies $\mathbb{P}^{N_i} \in_i G^N, \mathcal{Q}^{N_i} \notin_i G^N$ or $\mathbb{P}^{N_i} \notin_i G^N, \mathcal{Q}^{N_i} \in_i G^N$. Thus, (X, T_x^N) is a SNC – T_0 space.

Proposition 3.30:

Let (X, T_x^N) be a SNC – T_1 space if and only if for each $\mathbb{P}^{N_i} \neq \mathcal{Q}^{N_i} \in_i X$, $\mathcal{Ker}\{\mathbb{P}^{N_i}\}$ is SNC – weakly ultra separated from $\{\mathcal{Q}^{N_i}\}$ and $\mathcal{Ker}\{\mathcal{Q}^{N_i}\}$ SNC – weakly ultra separated from $\{\mathbb{P}^{N_i}\}$.

Proof: Proof is obvious.

Proposition 3.31:

Let (X, T_x^N) is a SNC – T_1 space if and only if for each $\mathbb{P}^{N_i} \in_i X$ then $\mathcal{Ker}\{\mathbb{P}^{N_i}\} = \{\mathbb{P}^{N_i}\}$.

Proof: Proof is obvious.

Proposition 3.32:

Let (X, T_x^N) is a SNC – T_1 space if and only if for each $\mathbb{P}^{N_i} \neq \mathcal{Q}^{N_i} \in_i X$ implies $\mathcal{Ker}\{\mathbb{P}^{N_i}\} \cap_2 \mathcal{Ker}\{\mathcal{Q}^{N_i}\} = \emptyset_3^N$.

4. Conclusions:

When we talk about the separation axioms, especially T_0, T_1, T_2 and Regular it was at the neutrosophic points $(\mathbb{P}^{N_1}, \dots, \mathbb{P}^{N_4})$, meaning that the talk here is local and about any point, such as in the classical topology spaces. From here, we can study the local function and other mathematical concepts studied in [8-12] in the stable neutrosophic crisp typological spaces. Moreover, we can extend the discussion in this paper by connecting the ideas in these previous works [13-17].

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